

TEACHING PRINCIPLES OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGY THEORY AND PRACTICE IN DUAL EDUCATION CONDITIONS

Siddikova Sadokat Ghaforovna

rector of the Bukhara Institute of Engineering and Technology, doctor of philosophy in pedagogical sciences, associate professor, sadoqats@mail.ru

Saidjonova Parvina Shukhratovna

is an independent researcher at the Bukhara Institute of Engineering and Technology, parvina.saidjanova@icloud.com
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14282059>

Abstract. This article analyzes the teaching principles of the theory and practice of pedagogical technology in the conditions of dual education. The article discusses the study of pedagogical technologies that help the effective implementation of dual education and their integration into the educational process. Practical application of pedagogical technology and educational methods, as well as the role of teaching principles in the dual education system are given in detail. This research serves as an important resource for teachers and students to develop pedagogical approaches and methodologies necessary to create an effective educational system.

Keywords: dual education, pedagogical technology, teaching principles, teaching methods, teaching process, practice, pedagogical approaches, educational system, educational theory.

Introduction. The principles of pedagogical technologies in the process of dual education were present in all eras, in any teaching and upbringing process, but the understanding and selection, management, theory and practice of pedagogy of these technologies were excluded. In fact, in the practice of higher educational institution, the principles of pedagogical technologies are implemented through the activity of the teacher, using books, technical equipment, teaching methods as material means, or pre-planned educational process [1]. At the same time, the principles of pedagogical technology are not a rigid, compressed, shallow project, but the result of creativity, creativity, dedication, and activity that allows to evaluate a number of factors that determine the effectiveness of education and upbringing.

1. In the conditions of dual education, the theory and practice of pedagogical technology teaching principles are important. These principles help to effectively organize the educational process and integrate academic and practical knowledge of students. Let's review these principles briefly:

3. Integrated teaching - in this dual education, theoretical knowledge is inextricably linked with practical activities and allows students to apply theoretical knowledge in practical work.

4. Active teaching methods - the principle that determines the importance of using methods such as interactive methods, group work, and problem assignments to ensure the active participation of students.

5. Personalized teaching - developing and implementing teaching strategies that match the individual needs of students. This improves students' specialization and career readiness.

6. Creativity and innovation - encourages creative and innovative activities of students in the educational process, encourages them to develop new ideas, projects and solutions.

7. Self-assessment and reflection - assessment of students' own activities during the study process, ensures the development of reflexive thinking, which helps to increase educational efficiency.

8. Communication and cooperation - ensures the establishment of effective communication between students and teachers, the introduction of methods based on cooperation.

Literature review. Implementation of these principles in the conditions of dual education ensures students' learning and future profession, in particular, successful professional activity [2].

According to the scientific and theoretical conclusions of scientists, the following cases are taken into account when determining the principles of "pedagogical technology":

- educational goal suitable for students of existing society;
- objective conditions of the didactic process;
- conditions under which the educational process takes place.

This development creates the need to integrate the educational process in higher education with the activities of production enterprises, to accelerate the process of dual education and to optimize training. This is, firstly, to minimize the gap between science and education, both quantitatively and qualitatively, and secondly, to revise the content of education, that is, to reduce the volume and complexity of information that students should acquire. , for this, it requires students to develop active, independent, creative thinking, self-evaluation, and self-education. This includes, according to the teaching of psychological theory, building dual education on the basis of a high level of difficulty, increasing the speed of acquiring information, increasing the amount of information of a

theoretical and generalizing nature, developing active, independent, creative thinking in students. It refers to the issues of stroking.

Research methodology. Based on some theoretical conclusions of pedagogical scientists N. Sayidakhmedov, M. Ochilov, it can be recognized that the theory and practice of pedagogical technology is based on the following principles [4]:

1. The principle of the integrity and unity of the purpose, content and teaching process of education. This principle requires that all components of the pedagogical system should be organized in one direction, that is, as a whole. For example, the sole goal of an independent republic is to educate a mature generation of specialists with deep scientific knowledge, high spiritual and moral qualities, and high qualifications. This goal naturally changed the educational system, and the changed educational system changed the content of education as a social order, the documents defining it are curriculum, textbooks, study guides based on the educational program. led to creation and is being created. This situation, in turn, requires updating the content of new textbooks and manuals, the ways and means of conveying information to the younger generation, and if they are created and used in practice, the conditions will be created for the sole purpose, order of society - to educate a mature generation. . Therefore, if the components of the educational process: goal, content, form, method are approached as a whole, pedagogical technologies will achieve their goal.

2. The principle of designing the educational process and implementing the project. It is known that the teaching process is a controlled process. According to the laws of pedagogic technology, the teacher should implement in the direction of the goal, activity, result, that is, he should have the ability to foresee the result of education, study-teaching issues and solve them. should be familiar with the laws of technology design. The designed technology should be introduced within the time allotted to the subject of the lesson, and the selected additional information should correspond to the strength, level of knowledge, age and individual characteristics of students [5].

3. The principle of scientificity, modernity and guaranteed final result. This principle requires the constant application of active methods of education through forms, methods, and means of education that have been tested in experience and are suitable for good results. As a result of continuous research, a teacher-researcher can acquire the skills of rational application of didactic

information. The use of scientifically based didactic innovations in the school experience recognizes modernity.

4. The principle of the priority of the student's interest in education. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" contains the principle of humane and democratic nature of education. This principle requires the introduction of the principle of ensuring the priority of the student's interest in education in the system of pedagogical technologies. Based on this, it is necessary to pay more attention to the independent study, reading, and analysis of students in the educational process. Organizing students' curiosity and initiative in acquiring knowledge, skills, and abilities is one of the important directions of pedagogical technology.

5. The principle of completeness of teaching in pedagogical technology. This principle requires that the student, after studying each topic, begins to master a new topic in order to be able to apply it in practice. It offers to determine the quality of learning experiences of the student and the coefficient of learning. If the student's knowledge index is higher than the passing score, then the training has reached its goal, it is completed, that is, the student has acquired knowledge, has the ability and skills to apply it in practice. If the level of knowledge is below the passing score, the information will not be fully mastered, and this situation will prevent the acquisition of practical skills in the enterprise. This result indicates that the educational goal and the expected result have not been achieved.

It is known that in the higher education institutions of our country, the students' mastery rate is set as high for satisfactory, good and excellent grades. According to teacher scientist N. Sayidakhmedov, $Bk \geq 0.7$ is sufficient for the current stage of development of educational materials by students. But this indicator is not enough for the "explosion effect" scientifically based and foreseen by the President of the Republic. Because it will not be enough for the next stage of development. Therefore, the higher the absorption coefficient, the higher the value of the development. Accordingly, the scientist defines the satisfactory coefficient as $Bk \leq 0.7$, so that the student's knowledge coefficient is higher than the clearly defined standard, which corresponds to the principle of completeness of teaching. This is one of the important conditions of the new pedagogical technology [4].

6. The principle of elasticity. The new pedagogical technology is based on the features of the technological process based on modern demands and needs. It is known that time, development, and production change and develop. The

existing technologies are forced to change the production tools and workplaces depending on the type of product, and it will be changed immediately. This quality indicator of technology is called elasticity. In the process of education and training, the change of the era and the transition to a new stage of development lead to a change in the goals and tasks of education and training. This change, in turn, led to a change in the content, form, methods, and means of education.

They cause changes in pedagogical technologies. This reason allows the teacher to change the structure of the educational process in accordance with the diagnostic purpose. This is the basis of the flexibility principle of the new pedagogical technology.

7. The principle of acceleration or optimization of the pedagogical process. It is known that in recent years the speed of development of science has reached its highest indicators. During the last decades, the content of scientific activity has increased significantly. According to scientists of the 21st century, 3/3 of the knowledge accumulated during the entire history of mankind was collected only during this period. This testifies to the rapid development of science and the rapid growth of scientific and technical information. This is very different from the situation of the past 25-30 years in terms of the speed and volume of information growth.

Analysis and results. The form of education in the theory of pedagogy, the appropriate use of educational tools, the choice of interactive methods suitable for the content of education serve to improve the content of teaching and increase the quality of education.

During the educational process, the teacher should educate the student's skills in organizing activities, independent reading, thinking, analysis, and application. Also, the teacher should have developed the skills of developing and using didactic materials that increase the efficiency of using information technologies and technical tools in the process of teaching and learning. This, of course, requires the teacher to have the ability to understand entrepreneurship, innovation and use it clearly.

For this, the teacher should be confused about which topic to cover in the course of the lesson, what kind of education or the use of information media and educational methods can bring high results to education.

This is achieved only through the principle of intensification and optimization of pedagogical technology. Thus, the principles of pedagogical technology described above are used to build the educational process in

educational institutions on a scientific basis, based on the advantages and opportunities of the dual education system, students' independent assimilation of information, analysis, skills and qualifications acquired in enterprises helps to turn it into personal property and to form personal qualities on this basis [6].

Conclusions and suggestions. The results of the analysis presented in the article show that the effective use of pedagogical technologies in the conditions of dual education is important for the quality development of the teaching process. Pedagogical technology theory and practice is based on the principles of teaching and serves to ensure close cooperation between students and teachers. Also, for the successful implementation of the dual education system, it is necessary to further strengthen cooperation between educational institutions and the field of production. The correct application of pedagogical principles in the teaching process helps to provide students with practical skills and increases their employability. In the future, it is possible to increase the efficiency of the educational system by further expanding dual education and improving pedagogical technologies.

In conclusion, it can be said that studying the principles of new pedagogical technologies in the organization of dual education and using its important factors in the process of dual education allows to raise the quality of training of specialists to another level and it meets the requirements of modern education. , because, as noted above, to accelerate the work of teaching students using new pedagogical and information technologies and teaching principles, and on this basis, students and young people are knowledgeable, humanitarian, the way to positive actions is opened to form feelings of loyalty and hard work.

References:

1. Bakeyev, T. I. (2017). Dual ta'lim: nazariya va amal. Toshkent: Uzbekiston Davlat Pedagogika universiteti.
2. Po'latov, Sh. N. (2021). Shaxsiylashtirilgan ta'lim: nazariy asoslar va amaliyot. Toshkent: Oliy ta'lim instituti.
3. Ruziyev, A. J. (2019). Dual ta'limning zamonaviy tendensiyalari. "Pedagogika va psixologiya" jurnali, 2(1), 45-50.
4. Сайидахмедов Н. Янги педагогик технология принциплари. - «Маърифат», 1999. – 45 б.
5. Султонова, М. А. (2020). Педагогик технологиялар ва уларнинг ўқитиш жараёнидаги аҳамияти. Тошкент: Олий ва ўрта махсус таълим вазирлиги.
6. Тухтаева З. Ш. Касб-хунар таълимида фанлараро узвийликни таъминлаш методикаси. – 2016.

7. To'xtayeva, Z., Usmonova, N., & Umedova, M. M. (2023). BO 'LAJAK MUHANDISLARNING LOYIHALASH KO 'NIKMALARIGA QO 'YILADIGAN KASBIY TALABLAR. Talqin va tadqiqotlar, 1(27).
8. Sh, T. Z. (2020). Integration of special subjects in higher education. International Engineering Journal For Research & Development, 5(3), 125-131.
9. Sharifovna, T. Z. (2019). ORGANIZATIONAL-METHODOLOGICAL INTER-OBJECTIVE INTEGRATIONS IN TEACHING SPECIAL DISCIPLINES. European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol, 7(12).

